

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Methyl Phenyl Sulphide by Chromium(VI) in Presence of Oxalic Acid

P. V. V. SATYANARAYANA* and G. V. RAMANA

Department of Chemistry, Nagarjuna University, Nagarjuna Nagar-522 510

Manuscript received 27 March 1989, accepted 3 May 1989

The kinetics of oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphide by chromium(VI) in aqueous acetic acid in presence of oxalic acid has been investigated. The order with respect to sulphide, chromium(VI) and oxalic acid was found to be each unity. The enhanced reactivity in presence of oxalic acid is explained by considering the rate-determining formation of a ternary complex of oxalic acid - chromium(VI) - sulphide.

HEXAVALENT chromium is known to function both as one- and two-electron oxidant depending on the substrate. These processes involve the intermediate valency states of chromium, i.e. chromium(V) and chromium(IV). Kinetics of oxidation of sulphides by Cr^{VI} in presence of perchloric acid has been reported and a mechanism involving one-electron transfer in the rate-determining step was envisaged for the oxidation process¹. Rocek and Hasan² reported the reduction of Cr^{VI} directly to Cr^{III} by a single step three-electron transfer in the co-oxidation of propan-2-ol and oxalic acid. As a part of the interest on the oxidation of sulphides by metal ion species, we in a preliminary investigation observed that the rate of oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphide (MPS) by chromium(VI) was enhanced in presence of added oxalic acid (oxH₂). Further, there was no such report on the oxidation of MPS, though co-oxidation was investigated with other organic substrates³⁻⁶. This prompted us for the detail kinetic investigation on the oxidation of MPS by Cr^{VI} in presence of oxH₂ and here we report our results.

Experimental

Acetic acid was purified over chromium trioxide. Oxalic acid, potassium dichromate and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Methyl phenyl sulphide was prepared and purified by employing known procedure. The kinetics were carried out in 20% acetic acid and 80% water mixture. The ionic strength was maintained by adding sodium perchlorate. The reaction was initiated by mixing equal volumes of MPS, oxH₂ and Cr^{VI} solutions which were pre-equilibrated in a thermostat. The course of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted chromium(VI) iodometrically⁷. Double-distilled water was used for all purposes.

In a typical experiment, MPS, oxH₂ and chromium(VI) solutions were mixed in 20% aqueous

acetic acid. The mixture was kept in a thermostat for 2 days at 30°. One of the products obtained was identified⁸ as carbon dioxide. The reaction mixture was worked out and the product isolated was found to be methyl phenyl sulphoxide by comparison with a specimen of the authentic sample (tlc and nmr spectra).

Results and Discussion

The kinetics were carried out under second order conditions due to solubility problem of MPS in the chosen medium. The rate constants for the oxidation of MPS by Cr^{VI} in presence of oxH₂ are given in Table 1. Variation in [MPS] or [Cr^{VI}] has

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [MPS] AND [Cr^{VI}] ON CHROMIC ACID OXIDATION OF MPS—OXALIC ACID SYSTEM

Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (20 : 80), Temp.=30°, [oxalic acid]= 5.4×10^{-4} M

[MPS] $\times 10^4$ M	[Cr ^{VI}] $\times 10^4$ M	k_{expt} $\times 10 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.0	0.92	4.24
1.7	0.92	4.31
3.5	0.92	4.40
4.5	0.92	4.36
6.1	0.92	4.36
5.7	1.17	4.46
5.7	2.24	4.41
5.7	3.51	4.39
5.7	4.67	4.46
5.7	5.89	4.40

no appreciable effect on the calculated second order rate constants indicating that the order with respect to MPS and Cr^{VI} is each unity. Table 2 presents the second order rate constants for the oxidation of MPS by Cr^{VI} at varying [oxH₂]. The rate was found to increase with increase in [oxH₂] and the order with respect to oxalic acid was also found to be unity from the linear plot of log k vs log [oxalic acid] ($r=0.998$). The oxidation of oxalic acid by Cr^{VI} under the same experimental conditions was

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING [OXALIC ACID] ON CHROMIC ACID OXIDATION OF MPS—OXALIC ACID SYSTEM

Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (20 : 80), Temp.=30°, [Cr^{VI}]=1.48 × 10⁻⁴ M, [MPS]=6.17 × 10⁻⁴ M

[Oxalic acid] × 10 ⁴ M	k _{expt} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
2.4	1.85
5.4	4.54
7.5	6.89
9.3	9.14
12.5	13.20
16.8	20.40
19.6	24.70

found to be almost negligible. The rate of oxidation of MPS by Cr^{VI} was also investigated under the same experimental condition and found to be 8.37 × 10⁻³ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹.

The oxidation of the mixed substrate system by Cr^{VI} was not influenced by the variation of ionic strength indicating the rate-determining step may involve an ion-dipole or dipole-dipole interaction. The rate of oxidation was influenced by the variation in the solvent composition. The rate was found to increase with increase in acetic acid content in the reaction medium.

The effect of the added acrylonitrile on the rate of oxidation of the triad system has been studied and found that there is no influence of the added acrylonitrile and the rate constants remained practically unchanged. Further, no polymerisation was observed. This observation cannot be taken as evidence for the absence of free radicals. In the acidic conditions it is not possible to detect free radicals as their own oxidation is catalysed by acid⁹. Similar results were obtained in the presence of free radical scavengers in the co-oxidation of secondary alcohols and oxalic acid with Cr^{VI}⁸.

Chandra *et al.*¹⁰ reported that the chromic acid oxidation of oxalic acid can be effectively prevented by the presence of aluminium nitrate. This effect is obviously due to the ability to form complex with oxalic acid and thus prevent the formation of oxalic acid-chromium(VI) complex. As we believe that the formation of oxalic acid-chromic acid complex plays a crucial role in the oxidation MPS, we were interested in testing whether the presence of aluminium salt would prevent the co-oxidation reaction from occurring and the results are given in Table 3. The result is in agreement with the assumption that the chromic acid-oxalic acid complex is an intermediate in the co-oxidation reaction.

Mechanism: Chromic acid forms a 1 : 1 complex with oxalic acid (C₁). It is proposed that the complex reacts with MPS in the rate-determining step to produce another complex C₂. The complex C₂ on solvolysis yields the products sulphoxide, carbon dioxide, •CO₂ radical and Cr³⁺ species. The

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ALUMINIUM NITRATE ON CHROMIC ACID OXIDATION OF MPS—OXALIC ACID SYSTEM

Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (20 : 80), Temp.=30°, [Cr^{VI}]=1.48 × 10⁻⁴ M, [MPS]=6.17 × 10⁻⁴ M

[Oxalic acid] × 10 ⁴ M	[Aluminium nitrate] × 10 ³ M	k _{expt} × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.0	0.0	8.37
5.4	0.0	446.00
5.4	1.0	8.48
5.4	1.5	8.42

free radical can then undergo further oxidation with either free or complex chromium(VI), producing carbon dioxide and Cr⁵⁺ (Scheme 1). The mechanism involves a two-electron oxidation of MPS and a one-electron oxidation of oxalic acid in the complex C₂.

The rate law could be written as

$$\frac{-d \text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}}{dt} = kK [\text{MPS}] [\text{oxH}_2] [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = kK [\text{MPS}] [\text{oxH}_2]$$

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